

RDA & External Reproducibility Efforts

This document highlights ongoing efforts related to computational reproducibility both within and outside of RDA. Aspects of computational reproducibility have been categorized under seven themes: policy, software & tools, professional development & training, standards, best practices & definitions, evaluation, reproducibility workflows, and reproducibility services. The groups included were either identified by RDA Reproducibility Interest Group members or added by a member from their respective group. This is a living document and subject to additions and changes as new groups or aspects of computational reproducibility are discovered.

If you would like to contribute a group or new theme, please contact the [RDA Reproducibility IG Co-Chairs](#).

The information collected in this document was provided by RDA community members and members of the external groups. RDA Reproducibility Interest Group co-chairs formatted and synthesized the information from the following documents:

- [Overview: Reproducibility work at RDA and beyond, May 2024](#)
- [RDA Reproducibility IG mapping](#)
- [RDA P23 Reproducibility IG: Mapping Activity](#)

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The Google Docs version can be found here: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1MRtAzKt5ZLzREAhS33NmlWcSbnE7L_X7JWN39WsMf7c/edit?usp=sharing

Group Name	Aspect of Computational Reproducibility						
	Policy	Software & Tools	Professional Development & Training	Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions	Evaluation	Reproducibility Workflows	Reproducibility Services
RDA							
FAIRsharing WG							
Metadata IG							
FAIR Principles for Research Hardware IG							
Engaging Researchers with Data IG							
Evaluation of Research IG							
Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG							
FAIR for Research Software & Software Source Code IG							
Funders Forum and Funders Interest Group							

FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG							
External							
iRise							
ACM Reproducibility EIG							
Cornell Social Science Center							
cascad							
Institute for Replication							
UKRN							
TIER2							
ScreenIT							
Project TIER							
TRACE							
Social Science Data Editors							
CODECHECK							
SciScore							
FAIRER Data Management							
DLF Assessment Interest Group - Content Reuse Working Group							
Local Contexts							
French Reproducible Research Network							
Canadian Research Data Centre Network							
Knowledge Exchange							
SciCodes							

RDA FAIRsharing Working Group

Description

The [RDA FAIRsharing WG](#) focuses on reproducibility through the lens of the FAIR Principles, specifically by delivering a curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies, across all disciplines and for all stakeholders. FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/>) guides consumers to discover, select and use these resources with confidence, producers to make their resource more discoverable, more widely adopted and cited, and powers third party tools by providing trustworthy content to promote standards and databases.

Fig. 1. FAIRSharing.org Main Page

Categories

- Policy ▾
- Professional Development & Training ▾
- Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾
- Reproducibility Workflows ▾
- Reproducibility Services ▾

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

Computational reproducibility is a core facet of FAIR and one that FAIRsharing supports by providing its content to a variety of stakeholders. Our content is accessible to all third-party tools and is key in the development of many types of tools, such as machine-actionable DMPs, DMP creation tools and FAIR assistance and assessment tools. FAIRsharing can also be used to compare our machine-actionable metadata for standards, databases and policies. For example, our policy registry makes the FAIR-enabling attributes of policies more explicit and comparable by both humans and machines, which could make monitoring the policy landscape more straightforward and efficient in the years to come ([blog post](#)).

We have also co-created the [TIER2 Editorial Reference Handbook](#) with over 20 journals ([find out more](#)), a service for both publishers and authors in the context of the manuscript submission workflow. This Handbook contributes towards a common understanding of what is required by scholarly journals and publishers to assist reproducibility and FAIRness in practice by defining the agreed checks that are fundamental to enable FAIRness and reproducibility for all objects (e.g. datasets, code, material) in a publication. The Handbook targets in-house editorial staff managing the manuscripts, but also benefits reviewers, authors and service providers by making the fundamental checks and the requirements transparent and understandable to them. The FAIRsharing WG is also engaging with DMP initiatives such as the [Common API for maDMPs WG](#) to ensure that our content is available within maDMPs (see also our [collaboration with DSW](#)).

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

The FAIRsharing mission is to increase guidance to consumers of standards, databases, repositories, and data policies, to accelerate the discovery, selection and use of these resources; and increase producer satisfaction in terms of resource visibility, reuse, adoption and citation.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

In addition to technical challenges, continuing the community's efforts on social challenges is key. FAIRsharing aims to foster a culture change within the research community into one where the use of standards, databases and repositories for FAIRer data is pervasive and seamless. To do this, we need to better promote the existence and value of these resources.

RDA FAIRsharing Working Group

The RDA FAIRsharing WG has produced a registry for data and metadata standards, databases, and policies to assist researchers in understanding and selecting these resources for implementation as part of their data management and sharing plans. The registry promotes both the FAIR Principles and transparent research practices which align with reproducibility efforts by increasing access and visibility of the processes and products of research projects. In addition, the RDA FAIRsharing WG is working on educational materials to promote standards and best practices identified within the registry.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

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RDA Metadata Interest Group

Description

The [RDA Metadata IG](#) seeks to share and develop best practices with regard to collecting, codifying and syndicating documentation – including that relating to reproducibility – so that it is machine-actionable in as many contexts as possible. One major barrier to computational reproducibility is that researchers may not have a good idea of what information is required (and in what detail) to enable others to reproduce their computations, and even less time and inclination to commit the effort required to record it all.

Categories

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

The RDA Metadata IG concerns itself with all aspects of metadata for research data. In particular, it works to coordinate the efforts of the RDA WGs concerned with metadata to produce a coherent approach to metadata. With respect to computational reproducibility, researchers may not have a good idea of what information is required (and in what detail) to enable others to reproduce their computations, and even less time and inclination to commit the effort required to record it all. The Metadata IG can be a source of information on, and a vehicle for the promotion of, metadata standards that are necessary or highly desirable to permit computational reproducibility.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

Computational reproducibility depends on detailed documentation describing how the original computation was accomplished. The Metadata IG seeks to share and develop best practices with regard to collecting, codifying and syndicating documentation – including that relating to reproducibility – so that it is machine-actionable in as many contexts as possible.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

We have no collective view on this. Alex Ball's (Metadata IG co-chair) personal view is that scholarship that relies on the computation of data should be computationally reproducible as far as possible, but recognises that there are limits. Exact reproducibility may not be possible where measures have been taken to prevent the (re-)identification of participants, for example, or with models of complex and chaotic systems where small changes deep in the processing can lead to noticeable differences in the result.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

One major barrier is that researchers may not have a good idea of what information is required (and in what detail) to enable others to reproduce their computations, and even less time and inclination to commit the effort required to record it all. For good practices to be adopted, it is important that the people bearing the cost of enabling reproducibility also enjoy the benefits that arise from it: if the benefits are only enjoyed by others, it will be a hard sell.

RDA Metadata Interest Group

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

What sorts of metadata do you feel are necessary or highly desirable to permit computational reproducibility?

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RDA FAIR Principles for Research Hardware Interest Group

Description

The [FAIR4RH](#) Interest Group (IG) aims to contribute to better recognition of Research Hardware (RH) as a valid research output. The IG also aims to raise awareness about the importance of sharing exhaustive documentation of RH, which contributes directly to the RH reproducibility. Depending on the domain application - RH can be strongly interdependent with software (in some cases software is required to run the hardware). Therefore, computational reproducibility specifically is essential to achieve reproducibility of an RH or of a method that utilizes RH.

Categories

[Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions](#) ▾

[Reproducibility Workflows](#) ▾

The FAIR Principles for Research Hardware IG defined research hardware, and is currently revising FAIR principles in the specific hardware-related context. Also, FAIR4RH will work on highlighting the importance of robust documentation as a key part in both making research hardware FAIR and in ensuring the reproducibility of research conducted with particular research hardware.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

Information about Research Hardware (RH) is generally lacking, *i.e.*, it is not properly disseminated, and efforts to provide it are inadequately incentivized in the current academic landscape. At the same time, development and dissemination of hardware (from prototypes towards market-ready designs) could be facilitated using open source hardware practices and FAIR principles.

By defining research hardware as “a physical object developed as part of or for a research process” (our first endorsed output from [2024](#)) and by adapting the FAIR data principles to RH (to which our current efforts are oriented), we aim at raising awareness on the importance of sharing an exhaustive documentation package of RH within FAIR4RH IG. Concurrently, we hope to contribute to better recognition of RH as a valid research output, regardless of its openness. Moreover, we are not dealing with “computational reproducibility” per se. However, FAIR principles for RH can contribute to the RH reproducibility, especially in the sense of proper documentation: “To improve reproducibility, it is imperative that these novel instruments are properly documented” as stated by Bowman ([2023](#)). Moreover, RH can be strongly interdependent with software (in some cases software is required to run the hardware), so computational reproducibility is essential to achieve overall reproducibility of an RH and reproducibility of a method that utilizes RH.

In addition, we consider FAIR RH an enabler of computer reproducibility. Specifically, we think communities that grow around open and FAIR RH will develop data standards, testing procedures (also referred as hardware process), and software-related practices linked to the RH. For example, researchers using the same data collection instrument would work with the same data structure. Such practices will then, in turn, facilitate computational reproducibility.

RDA FAIR Principles for Research Hardware Interest Group

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

We cannot speak on behalf of all members of RDA FAIR4RH IG, but yes all scholarship should be computationally reproducible by default. However, we do not feel that RH should be reproducible by default as RH definition: (1) do not envision RH to be documented at all and (2) do not consider RH complimented with their documentation package (hardware design files, software, documentation, and branding).

On the other hand, disseminated research hardware and especially scientific hardware should be FAIR, shared under an open license, and reproducible. While some initiatives build on the definition of open source hardware to foster reproducibility, our group is focusing on the definition of FAIR for RH with the similar objective to make RH and the computational process linked to them reproducible.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Two main challenges specifically related to RH we can think of are that: (1) RH can be dependent on hardware components that are not always easily accessible (e.g., obsolete and proprietary components) and (2) that hardware reproducibility can come with costs (in comparison to the software).

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Are FAIR principles required for reproducible research? Would you consider expanding reproducibility outside of the computational realm and how do you see RH reproducibility? Does the RH definition make sense in your reproducibility context? What should we consider for aligning FAIR principles for RH? Is openness a requirement for reproducible output, and what needs to be open in this context (hardware documentation, production process, or community)?

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RDA Engaging Researchers with Data Interest Group

Description

The [RDA Engaging Researchers with Data IG](#) is concerned with the social and networking aspects of reproducibility and aims to support and embed best practices at both the researcher and institutional level. Challenges to achieving this include cultural change, incentivisation and the need

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

The RDA Engaging Researchers with Data IG is concerned with the social and networking aspects of reproducibility as part of the group's broader goals to support best practices around research data. Our

RDA Engaging Researchers with Data Interest Group

for expert support. The IG is interested in coordinating the dissemination of best practice and hearing about the outputs produced by other groups that support this work.

Categories

Professional Development & Training ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

A key motivation of the group is to build social bridges that enable sharing and reuse of data. This is achieved through engagement with research communities to develop their understanding and involvement in what is best practice and how to implement it.

group's main activities involve collecting, documenting, and sharing case studies of programmes and activities that develop researcher skills and their understanding of best practice.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

All researchers and institutions are aware of best practice around computational reproducibility, are incentivised to implement/support it, and have access to open tools and resources that facilitate it.

The rationale for this vision is that all researchers and their places of work should understand the value of reproducibility and how to implement it, which are both within the scope of our IG to disseminate. However, not all scholarship can be computationally reproducible: some data collection opportunities are ephemeral by nature.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Institutions, funders, and other stakeholders will need expert support to:

- understand and communicate the value of reproducibility across different research field and contexts;
- define the circumstances under which reproducibility should be expected; and
- develop incentive and monitoring systems that create the minimum possible extra friction on research activity.

For researchers, cultural change may be required to make reproducible research the norm. The success of this will depend on articulating the value of reproducibility and incentivising it correctly; otherwise the perception will be that reproducibility is another administrative burden that detracts from the 'actual research'.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

- What are the group's priorities in terms of outputs/activities?
- How can we ensure coordination between relevant IGs, particularly around dissemination of best practice.

RDA Evaluation of Research Interest Group

Description

The evolution of the evaluation of research from being mostly bibliographic index-based is now recognized to be indispensable to enable Open Science. In the same way that Open Science promotes the open sharing of FAIR data and other research outputs, evaluators must also value and consider these outputs as part of the wider research evaluation framework. The RDA is an appropriate forum for addressing the evolving requirements of research evaluation as they relate to Open Science practices. RDA's reach across the international community, including research organisations and funders, can help to facilitate and align a global discussion of research evaluation, drawing on data experts from a range of domains.

The [RDA Evaluation of Research IG](#) organises the discussion on the subject in the RDA, in particular as it relates to data, and also in relation to RDA activities on research software.

Categories

Policy ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

Evaluation ▾

The EoR group intersects with reproducibility as this is part of open science and the drive for evaluation to take into account open practices. The group aims to influence policy and generate discussion on all aspects of evaluation and how it can be applied to reproducible research evaluation.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

RDA Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) Interest Group

Description

The [RDA Sharing Rewards and Credit \(SHARC\) IG](#) is an interdisciplinary group with the aim of advancing the inclusion of Open Science in research evaluation to ensure it is rewarding for researchers to practice. The group is in the process of publishing two papers that detail their findings

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

The RDA Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG is an interdisciplinary group with the aim of

RDA Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) Interest Group

and recommendations and would value discussions on the role relationship between rewards and credit and computational reproducibility.

Categories

Policy -

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions -

Evaluation -

Reproducibility is an open science activity and therefore intersects with SHARC as it can be considered a potential path for encouraging “the adoption of data sharing and open science activities-related criteria in the research evaluation process.” With knowledge of how credit for open science is structured, the groups can work on how computational reproducibility fits in.

fostering the implementation of rewarding paths and encouraging the adoption of data sharing/ Open Science (OS) activities-related criteria in the research evaluation process at the institutional, national and European / international levels, and also the goal of providing guidance for researchers and recommendations to critical actors in the academic rewarding scheme.

The IG’s focus is not directly related to computational reproducibility but a number of the findings and recommendations from the IG support the advancement of computational reproducibility in research.

What is your/your organization’s vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

That our findings/recommendations will drive further adoption of open science and FAIR practices.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

While our survey findings and recommendations are a resource for the range of stakeholders we address, from funders to publishers and institutions, still, these stakeholders face challenges ranging from resource dependent to cultural to sociotechnical to achieve the recommendations presented.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

What relationship do you see between sharing rewards and credit with computational reproducibility?

Note: The RDA SHARC IG is in the process of publishing two papers that will detail our findings and recommendations. For a recent presentation of our work to the Evaluation of Research IG, see <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Py2iVLE8rr-ZskzjDO6qzcZ8g67Hx7VP/view>.

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RDA FAIR for Research Software & Software Source Code Interest Group

Description

The [FAIR4RS WG](#) is completed, but the [RDA Software Source Code Interest Group](#) is the maintenance home for the principles. Software has become essential for research. To improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of research software, it is desirable to develop and apply a set of FAIR Guiding Principles for software. Many of the high-level FAIR data principles can be directly applied to research software by treating software and data as similar digital research objects. However, specific characteristics of software – such as its executability, composite nature,

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it’s related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization’s vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

RDA FAIR for Research Software & Software Source Code Interest Group

and continuous evolution and versioning – make it necessary to revise and extend the original data principles.

Categories

Software & Tools -

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions -

Reproducibility Workflows -

Reproducibility Services -

The group contributes to conversations relating to the meaning of reproducibility when applied to software, and questions concerning the execution of software and code in the context of computational reproducibility.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

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RDA Funders Forum and Funders Interest Group

Description

The [RDA Funders Forum](#) is a closed, informal coordination group of agencies/organizations that fund research and research infrastructure that meet before each RDA Plenary to discuss issues of particular relevance to Funders (contact [Matthew Lucas](#), co-chair). The open [RDA Funders Interest Group](#) then brings some of these issues/topics to the broader RDA community for discussion in order to increase dialogue between funders and other stakeholders.

Categories

Policy -

These two groups provide forums (at the appropriate level) for funders to discuss policy related to research data and open science and seek feedback from other stakeholders at RDA as appropriate. This helps to inform policy and funding decisions.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

RDA FAIRification of Genomic Annotations Working Group

Description

[FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG](#) is a life science domain-centric WG that aims to harmonize and FAIRify metadata that pertains to "genomic annotations", a particular type of genomics summary data can describe main findings from a variety of heterogeneous data sources. See [our poster](#) from the current RDA Plenary for an overview of the WG plans. We plan to set up a community infrastructure to harmonize metadata from historical and new data sources. The aim is to set up solutions to allow such harmonized metadata to be deposited in public repositories, and allow search services to harvest such metadata and provide search capabilities through some form of standardized API.

Contact: [Sveinung Gundersen](#)

Categories

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

Software & Tools ▾

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Reproducibility Services ▾

The end goal of the WG is to improve discoverability and reuse of data, including reproducibility of datasets/analyses. A particular use case is to allow for researchers to deposit metadata pertaining to datasets they have used for their analyses back into the same infrastructure, and then make them available for reuse, and simplify reproducibility.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

iRise

Description

[iRISE \(Improving Reproducibility in Science\)](#) is a three-year EU-funded project on research reproducibility. Among other things, we are implementing and assessing a computational reproducibility review intervention and trying to address the evidence gap for computational

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

iRISE (Improving Reproducibility in Science) is a three-year EU-funded project on research

iRise

reproducibility review. We are looking for volunteers to participate in our group of reproducibility checkers.

Fig. 2. iRise Work Packages Model

Categories

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

iRISE are working on a number of different interventions with publishers to test out the types of actions publishers can take to improve the reproducibility of the articles they publish. The types of intervention include RCTs, contacting authors with actions to improve reproducibility, and peer review of computational analyses.

reproducibility. Among other things, we are implementing and assessing a computational reproducibility review intervention. This intervention will be done in partnership with scientific publishers and will be a randomised experiment. For more on the iRISE project:

<https://irise-project.eu/>.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Our intervention test is premised on the idea that better mechanisms for quality control are possible and should be investigated for possible routine implementation.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

We are trying to address the evidence gap for computational reproducibility review and other interventions. Other challenges exist and include skills, technical platforms, resourcing, community norms, and incentives.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

We are looking for volunteers to participate in our group of reproducibility checkers. Volunteers will be co-authors on the paper describing the results in the end. If interested, please contact

gustav.nilsonne@ki.se.

Association of Computing Machinery (ACM) Emerging Interest Group on Reproducibility and Replicability (EIGREP)

Description

The Association of Computing Machinery (ACM) Emerging Interest Group on Reproducibility and Replicability ([EIGREP](#)) seeks to coalesce a vibrant scholarly community of researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders aiming to hold computing to the highest standards of reproducible research. The goal is (i) to contribute to the development of reproducibility standards, practices, and policies across the breadth of the scientific discovery pipeline, and the identification of barriers to their adoption, (ii) to promote the development and evaluation of tools, techniques, and methodologies that efficiently support reproducibility, and (iii) to encourage best practices across the ACM in consort with the larger computational research community.

Categories

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

Software & Tools ▾

Various conferences and SIGs (Special Interest Groups) at the ACM reward reproducibility. The EIGREP is working with reproducibility champions in the ACM SIGs to elevate the importance of their work, standardize practices, and develop tools across the various SIGs. This is a research community within the field of computer science.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

Fostering a diverse and inclusive community around the issues of reproducibility and replicability of computational research.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Reproducibility practices are central to community-wide objectivity.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Lack of education, lack of appropriate incentives, lack of appropriate tools.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Are you considering policies (beyond FAIR) to foster community-wide objectivity?

Cornell Social Science Center

Description

One of the core services of the [Cornell Center for Social Sciences](#) is replication and archiving. The service verifies and certifies the computational reproducibility of a study before publication. Clients are mostly Cornell authors, but they also perform data reviews for journals.

Questions & Answers

Briefly tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility. What are you trying to address, and how?

Cornell social scientists research to solve the world's most pressing social challenges. CCSS accelerates, enhances, and amplifies this research by providing advanced computing and other research infrastructure, seeding grants and fellowships, supporting quantitative and qualitative research, and building a diverse and inclusive community of scholars. One of its core services is Replication and Archiving. We verify and certify the computational reproducibility of a study before publication. Our clients are mostly Cornell authors, but we also do data reviews for journals.

Fig. 3. Results Reproduction Service at CCSS

Categories

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Reproducibility Services ▾

CCSS staff guide researchers through the process of preparing data for sharing and can perform verification to ensure reproducibility of research outputs. CCSS has implemented an internal workflow and standard submission process for conducting verification and reproducibility checks for both Cornell researchers and some journal partners. They also make the reproducibility packages available for download alongside [instructions](#) for how to reproduce results.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

- Agree all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default.
- Researchers are trained in preparing high-quality replication materials, which means knowledge of research data and code management.
- Long-term vision – for our Replication service to become obsolete because everyone practices good research data and code management.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

- Lack of awareness about the availability of such services.
- Promotion is key, but a client uptick could lead to scalability issues. Clients need to follow our guidelines for preparing replication packages to reduce the duration of verification.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

- None at the moment.

cascad

Description

Christophe Hurlin and Christophe Pérignon founded [cascad](#) in 2019 with a double objective: (1) to help individual researchers (mainly in economics and other quantitative social sciences) signal the reproducible nature of their research by granting reproducibility certificates and (2) to help other scientific actors (e.g., academic journals, universities, funding agencies, scientific consortia, data providers) verify the reproducibility of the research they publish, fund, or contribute to the production of.

cascad is a nonprofit research laboratory funded by the French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS) along with several universities and research institutions. While *cascad* is based in France, it collaborates with researchers and academic journals from all around the world. Its workforce comprises full-time reproducibility engineers, part-time graduate students, and a group of faculty oversees the operations and promotes the services offered.

Categories

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Reproducibility Services ▾

cascad offers a reproducibility service that grants a certificate to author-submitted manuscripts indicating the generated results from the underlying data and code are reproducible. Requirements and guidelines for submitting data and code for the reproducibility certification are outlined on their site and provide detailed guidance for ensuring the analyses are well-documented and transparent to facilitate reproducibility. Additional services include support for reproducibility certifications of research using confidential and/or restricted access data from entities such as federal statistical agencies.

Questions & Answers

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

The establishment of *cascad* was driven by two firm beliefs. First, we believe that for science to be taken seriously, there needs to be a serious commitment to reproducibility. To put it simply, if we want the chain of science to be strong and useful to society, reproducibility should not be its weakest link. Second, we hold the conviction that merely making code and data publicly accessible does not fully address the reproducibility challenge. We have come to this resolute belief after launching and managing RunMyCode (www.runmycode.org), a repository for code and data used by various economics and management journals. In this role, we frequently observed researchers failing to share all the essential components (code, data, explanations) necessary to regenerate their results. This was frequently due to hurdles such as copyright issues, non-disclosure agreements (NDAs), or concerns related to data privacy. Moreover, even when all components were available, other researchers frequently struggled to execute them, and occasionally failed entirely.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Launching and operating a third-party reproducibility verification service is costly. Colliard et al. (2023) decomposed the total costs between the fixed costs corresponding to the IT infrastructure (including software) and the variable costs corresponding to labor costs, computing costs, and the costs of accessing data. In a calibration exercise based on the actual number of papers published by 12 leading economics journals, they show that exploiting economies of scale could lower the average verification cost per paper from \$763 (separated verification teams) to \$330 (one single verification team for the 12 journals).

Our experience at *cascad* suggests that in addition to accessing restricted data, the most challenging and time-consuming task is to reconstruct the computing environment used by the original authors. Another challenge in practice is to be able to locate the results in the regenerated logfile because a surprisingly large fraction of code still does not automatically generate tables and figures (see Pérignon et al., 2024). These challenges suggest that one way to reduce verification costs is to increase automation in the verification process, raise awareness among researchers, and increase their coding skills.

The question of who should pay for the extra cost associated with reproducibility checks is also key. In the case of voluntary pre-submission verifications, it seems natural that the researchers requesting such certification will cover the associated costs. In the case of mandatory pre-publication checks, we propose that the cost should be shared between journals and research funding agencies. This subsidy

cascad

from research funding agencies is justified by the public good and externality effects of producing reproducible research (see Colliard et al., 2023).

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

We would like to ask them to contact us if they want to partner with us. While we face growing demand, our financial resources and staff remain limited, and we are not in a position yet to deliver at scale.

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Institute for Replication

Description

The [Institute for Replication](#) was started in 2022 to improve credibility in scientific research through activities aimed at reproducing and replicating the results reported in published articles within academic journals. Through this effort, I4R has developed guidance and teaching resources to educate and train researchers and students on best practices and approaches in open science and research reproducibility and replicability. I4R also maintains and promotes a repository for sharing reproductions and replications. Their current areas of focus are in economics, finance, and political science; however, they are in the process of expanding into other disciplines.

Meta Papers and Guidelines Reports Discussion Papers

Number	Title	Replicators	Actions
192	Response to Adjisse, Blimpo, and Castañeda Dower (2024)	Balán, Pablo & Bergeron, Augustin & Tourek, Gabriel & Weigel, Jonathan	⬇
191	Local Taxation and Development Finance in the DRC: A Comment on Balán et al. (2022)	Adjisse, Sossou & Blimpo, Moussa P. & Castañeda Dower, Paul	⬇
190	Do Experimental Asset Market Results Replicate? High-Powered Preregistered Replications of 17 Claims	Huber, Christoph & Holzmeister, Felix & Johannesson, Magnus & König-Kersting, Christian & Dreber, Anna & Huber, Jürgen & Kirchler, Michael	⬇
189	A comment on "The Effects of Racial Diversity in Citizen Decision-Making Bodies"	Kim, Do Won & Yang, Xilin & Kim, Do-Hoon	⬇
188	Letting Down the Team? Social Effects of Team Incentives - Reproduction Report of Babcock et al. (2015)	Pelloth, Daniel & Hoffmann, Patrick	⬇
187	Replication Report: Did Unconventional Interventions Unfreeze the Credit Market?	Coppo, Mattia & Luo, Shijia & Vazquez, Franciscot	⬇

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

The Institute for Replication (<https://i4replication.org/>)'s main goal is to promote and generate reproductions and replications. While I4R is not a journal, we have a board which actively recruits and selects replicators. We are also organizing reproducibility events all over the world: <https://i4replication.org/games.html>. As of now, we have 27 events scheduled this year and are expecting 1500 participants (faculty/postdoc/PhD students). We just released a meta paper combining our first 110 reproductions/replications: <https://econpapers.repec.org/paper/zbwi4rdps/107.htm>. Our next three (larger) meta papers are scheduled to be released within the next 18 months.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Our vision is to change norms through (i) mass reproductions/replications, (ii) education and training, (iii) engaging with original authors and (iv) collaborating with editors. For instance, we are now collaborating with Psychological Science and Nature Human Behaviour.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Having journal editors implementing data and code availability policies and enforcing the policy. Other than that, we have not faced any challenge that we could not easily overcome.

Institute for Replication

Fig. 4. Screenshot of Reports and Meta Papers Repository at I4R

Categories

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Professional Development & Training ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

I4R focuses on educating and training researchers on best practices and standards in reproducibility through the implementation of their Replication Games. These games bring teams of researchers together to reproduce the results from published manuscripts in the social sciences. I4R provides templates and report guidance for participants to share the results of their reproducibility attempt. All results are available for review via the I4R site in in-depth reports that describe the reproducibility process step-by-step as well as the findings.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Happy to collaborate with those interested in helping mass reproduce/replicate results.

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UK Reproducibility Network

Description

The [UK Reproducibility Network \(UKRN\)](#) is a grassroots movement aiming to foster open and robust research practices in the UK university sector by investigating the factors that contribute to robust research, promoting training activities, and disseminating best practice. We currently have two interest groups related to computational reproducibility - one focused on the “spotchecking” of research outputs and one focused on making computational reproducibility intelligible to a broad audience of researchers, beyond technical disciplines.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

The UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN) is a grassroots movement gathering representatives from about 70 Universities in the UK. Our aim is to foster open and robust research practices. We do this by investigating the factors that contribute to robust research, promoting training activities, and disseminating best practice. We also work collaboratively with various external stakeholders to ensure coordination of efforts across the sector. We seek to understand the factors that contribute to poor research reproducibility and replicability, and develop approaches to counter these, to improve the trustworthiness and quality of research. These issues affect all disciplines, so we aim for broad disciplinary representation. We believe that ongoing efforts to address these issues represent an opportunity to improve our research by reforming culture and practice.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

UK Reproducibility Network

About Community Resources Activities Join UKRN Contact

Primers

Our primer series is designed to introduce a broad audience to important topics in open and reproducible scholarship

Open research primers

Each primer includes an overview of the topic in the introductory “What?” section, reasons for undertaking these practices in the “Why?” section, followed by a longer “How?” section that provides guidance on how to do that open research behaviour practically.

Throughout the primers, there are embedded explanatory weblinks, and at the end of each is a collated list of links to useful further resources.

The primers are licensed under [Creative Commons license CC BY 3.0](#). You can link to, quote, share, and adapt the primers freely.

Fig. 5. Example of UKRN Reproducibility Resources

Categories

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions

Reproducibility Workflows

Reproducibility Services

The group is a leading “Reproducibility Network.” In addition to community building aspects of the UKRN (and other nationally-based RNs), this group is working on aspects of verification of computational reproducibility and several other efforts relating to the understanding, practice, and standards for open research, transparency, and reproducibility.

Computational reproducibility means different things to different people, and it isn’t the only aspect of reproducibility that is important to UKRN membership. However, we currently have two interest groups related to computational reproducibility, one focused on the “spotchecking” of research output at the level of an institution, which includes the reproducibility of scripted analyses, and a more recent one focused on making computational reproducibility intelligible to a broad audience of researchers, beyond technical disciplines.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

“Doing” computational reproducibility should not need a degree in computer science, and training people from varied disciplines can be challenging. Identifying the right level that people should care about can be tricky.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Any tips?

Check out a recent publication about the Croatian Reproducibility Network: Ursić, L., Bralić, N., Žuljević, M. F., Puljak, L., & Buljan, I. (2024). Exploring the understanding of reproducibility among stakeholders within academia and their expectations for a web-based education tool: A qualitative study. *Accountability in Research*, 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2024.2345723>

TIER2

Description

TIER2 is a three-year EU funded project investigating a range of methods, tools and practices related to increasing levels of reproducibility to systematically understand and enhance reproducibility in social, life, and computer sciences through targeted interventions. A key area of interest is “epistemic diversity” - that the meanings, relevance, and feasibility of “reproducibility” vary widely across research disciplines and methodologies. The project is looking at areas/interventions such as containerization tools, editorial checks for reproducibility, automated tools and policy instruments.

Fig. 6. TIER2 Strategic Priorities, taken from: Ross-Hellauer T (2023) Strategic priorities for reproducibility reform. PLOS Biology 21(1): e3001943. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3001943>

Categories

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it’s related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

Our project **TIER2** (EC Horizon-funded, 2023-2025), is investigating a range of methods, tools and practices related to increasing levels of reproducibility. A key concept for us is that of “epistemic diversity” (that the meanings, relevance, and feasibility of “reproducibility” vary widely across research disciplines and methodologies). A large part of our project is geared towards computational reproducibility, with areas of research including containerization tools for computationally reproducible workflows (in life and computer sciences), reproducibility checklists for computational social sciences, general purpose “reproducibility management plans” (extension of DMPs), an editorial handbook for reproducibility-related checks at journal-level, automated tools to monitor levels of re-use of data, code and other materials, as well as policy instruments (funder reproducibility promotion plans) and research into specific interventions (e.g., on measures to increase data-sharing).

What is your/your organization’s vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Our aim is to increase the reusability of research results and foster trust, integrity, and efficiency in processes of scholarship. By embracing epistemic diversity, our goal is to systematically understand and enhance reproducibility in social, life, and computer sciences wherever relevant and feasible through targeted interventions. A key element of this is computational reproducibility, which should be the default for all research to which the concept is applicable. However, we should also recognise that research can be computationally reproducible and still wrong – hence we must also continue to work on improving all areas of reproducibility more broadly, including the cultural disincentives that fuel questionable research practices.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Communities are now aware that action must all levels of research culture (c.f., Center for Open Science <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change>), from enabling infrastructure and tools, through training and awareness, to community building and normalisation, to incentives through reward/recognition or policy requirements. Targeting and coordinating action across all these areas is the ultimate challenge.

Achieving this vision is confronted with numerous challenges, including the diverse epistemological, social, and technical factors that influence reproducibility in different scientific contexts. Each discipline brings unique challenges that require tailored approaches to ensure effective reproducibility practices. With others, we also see a need for a brighter framing of the issue – from talk of “crisis” to “opportunity”. There is also a wealth of evidence on what works and where, that would benefit from

TIER2

Evaluation ▾

Software & Tools ▾

The project is focused on practices that increase reproducibility and the tools, guidelines etc needed for it. The project is currently trialling a workflow checklist with publishers and evaluating the behavioural changes needed in order for this checklist to be successfully implemented.

systematisation to identify priority areas for action and gaps in knowledge. Additionally, coordinating efforts across the broad stakeholder groups of researchers, publishers, and funders poses logistical and alignment challenges. These challenges necessitate continuous dialogue, adaptable strategies, and strong collaborative networks to implement effective reproducibility tools and practices across varied research contexts. Finally, in seeking to change systems we always run the risk of unintended consequences and these should be closely monitored.

Figure 6 outlines TIER2's specific key strategic priorities in addressing these challenges.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

- How are you addressing issues of epistemic diversity with regard to computational reproducibility (e.g., differences in cultures, standards, workflows, tools across disciplines)?
- When planning for computational reproducibility, what are the most important aspects that are not already covered in a Data Management Plan?
- How can researchers, institutions, funders, publishers, scholarly societies and others more effectively collaborate to increase computational reproducibility?
- What effective practices or tools have you implemented in your research to enhance computational reproducibility?

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ScreenIT

Description

[ScreenIT](#) created a collection of automated screening tools, combined into a single pipeline, to detect common problems or beneficial practices such as blinding, randomization, power calculations, limitations sections, open data, open code and common data visualization problems in published papers. FAIR predominantly addresses the question "Can I reuse this data?". We'd like to extend the conversation to data reuse by asking "Should I reuse this data?" and "How should I reuse this data responsibly?".

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

ScreenIT is a group of researchers and tool developers from around the world who create automated screening tools to detect common problems or beneficial practices in published papers. We predominantly focus on biomedical research, and our tools detect features like blinding, randomization, power calculations, limitations sections, open data, open code and common data visualization problems. We have combined our tools into a single pipeline. During the pandemic, we used this pipeline to screen and post public reports on more than 23,000 papers using the web annotation tool hypothesis.is. We have also used these tools to create a "Screen My Paper" website for our institution, which is undergoing testing. We hope that these reports help authors to make their

ScreenIT

Tools used to screen preprints

Tool	Screens For	Link & RRID
SciScore	Blinding, randomization, sample size calculations, sex/gender, ethics & consent statements, resources, RRIIDs	http://sciscore.com RRID:SCR_016251
ODDPub	Open data, open code	https://github.com/quest-bih/oddpub RRID:SCR_018385
Limitation-Recognizer	Author-acknowledged limitations	https://github.com/kilicogluh/limitation-recognizer RRID:SCR_018748
Barzooka	Bar graphs of continuous data	https://quest-barzooka.bihealth.org RRID:SCR_018508
JetFighter	Rainbow color maps	https://jetfighter.eclife.org RRID:SCR_018498
Trial Registration Number Screener	Confirms accuracy of clinical trial registration numbers registered in ClinicalTrials.gov	https://github.com/bgcarlisle/TRNScreener RRID:SCR_019211
scite	Retracted citations or citations of papers with erratums	https://www.scite.ai RRID:SCR_018568
rtransparent	Protocol registration, conflict of interest disclosures, funding disclosures	https://github.com/serghiou/rtransparent RRID_SCR019276
Seek and Blastn ^{8*}	Correct identification of nucleotide sequence	http://scigendetection.imag.fr/TPD52/ RRID:SCR_016625

*Some papers may be screened with Seek and Blastn, a semi-automated tool that requires human confirmation of results. Reports for Seek and Blastn are posted separately on PubPeer.

Abbreviations: RRID, research resource identifier

Fig. 7. Tools Used to Screen Preprints

Categories

Software & Tools ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

papers more transparent and reproducible. In the context of FAIR, our recent correspondence highlights the importance of detailed methods for responsible data reuse, and calls for those with relevant expertise to join us to develop guiding principles for responsible data reuse (<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-021-02906-8>). FAIR predominantly addresses the question "Can I reuse this data?" . We'd like to extend the conversation to data reuse, by asking "Should I reuse this data?" and "How should I reuse this data responsibly?".

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Publications routinely fail to include details that are essential for evaluating scientific rigor and the risk of bias. Compliance with reporting guidelines, outlining essential details that should be reported for different study types, remains poor. Our goal is to create automated tools to help authors improve reporting, before they submit their paper. As noted above, we'd also like to develop guiding principles for responsible data reuse.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Legacy manuscript submission systems are a major challenge. While we would like our tools to be integrated into journal submission systems, these systems are extremely inflexible and the costs for any changes are very high. Sustainability and maintaining the open source tools in the pipeline is also a challenge.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Our tools are focused on biomedicine and we don't have tools that are well suited for screening for features associated with rigorous science in computational papers. We would be interested in exploring opportunities to collaborate to develop tools for screening computational papers. As we are not computationally focused, we would also extend the conversation to include factors that are associated with reproducibility in fields that are not computational.

ScreenIT

Policy ▾

Evaluation ▾

The group is concerned with improving scientific manuscripts on a large scale. Publications routinely fail to include details that are essential for evaluating scientific rigor and the risk of bias and the group aims to create automated tools to help authors improve reporting, before they submit their paper, and to develop guiding principles for responsible data reuse.

Contact person: [Tracey Weissgerber](#), Berlin Institute of Health (BIH) at Charité QUEST Center for Responsible Research

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Project TIER

Description

[Project TIER](#) promotes the incorporation of computationally reproducible research methods in undergraduate and graduate-level quantitative methods training. In addition to working with individual faculty members to introduce reproducible methods in their own classes and research advising, the goal now is to promote systemic change by fostering the development of a community of educators with similar goals and shared norms.

Categories

Software & Tools ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Professional Development & Training ▾

Project TIER offers workshops, training, and resources for training professionals and students in reproducible research best practices and workflows. The project also produced the TIER Protocol which is a structured and robust resource for identifying and capturing all elements critical for both transparency and reproducibility of a research project.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

[Project TIER](#) promotes the incorporation of computationally reproducible research methods in undergraduate and graduate-level quantitative methods training.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Our vision is that it should be standard/ubiquitous to incorporate reproducible methods of data processing and analysis at all levels of the curriculum--from the first time students calculate group means or do a t-test through producing comprehensive reproduction documentation for doctoral dissertations.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Project TIER's greatest success has been working with individual faculty members to introduce reproducible methods in their own classes and research advising. Our goal now is to promote systemic change by fostering the development of a community of educators with similar goals and shared norms.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Project TIER

Who can Project TIER partner with to find ways to move from the model of working with individual instructors and find ways to facilitate collaboration across broader communities--departments, institutions, cross-institutional, or professional societies?

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TRACE

Description

The [TRACE project](#) is an NSF-funded project working on developing mechanisms and tools to support transparency and trust in computational research. It is a joint project between the University of Illinois, the Odum Institute at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, and Cornell University.

Fig. 8. TRACE System Overview

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

Our motivating question is the following:

How can we trust the integrity of results from research that relies on computations without repeating them?

Research communities across the sciences face a conundrum: to ensure the transparency and reproducibility of computational results, they require that authors share the data, code, and methods used to obtain them. However, without verification by repeating the computations, there is no guarantee that the author-provided artifacts are complete or can actually be used to reproduced results.

Particularly problematic are studies that employ [sensitive or proprietary data](#) for which access and reuse are restricted; [streaming, transient, or ephemeral data](#) that cannot be used to verify reproducibility due to their dynamic nature; or [very large-scale or specialized computational resources](#) available only to authorized users. In these cases, verification by repeating computations may not be possible.

TRACE presents a solution to this problem: certify the successful *original* execution of the computational workflow that produced the reported findings *in situ*. We call this **certified transparency**—a trustworthy record of computations signed by the systems within which they were performed.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Our vision is to increase trust in complex computational science through transparency, and by

TRACE

Categories

Software & Tools -

Reproducibility Workflows -

TRACE offers a conceptual model and technical specification for defining and describing TRACE systems and transparent research objects (TROs). Both the model and specification are tools to increase the integrity and transparency of research, particularly research conducted on secure or specialized compute resources, with sensitive or proprietary data, or ephemeral and transient data.

leveraging trust and credibility mechanisms where those exist. Even if we might not trust individual researchers, we may place higher (if not absolute) trust in government research centers or entire universities that enable those computations and data access. Developing a mechanism so that the trust chain behind computational science - and the limitations thereof - is clear, and expressive, is our goal.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Challenges arise in the particular vast diversity of computational methods, and computational infrastructure. We hope that our proposed mechanism - metadata structure and helper tools - is sufficiently flexible to be deployable in a large variety of environments and institutions. Institutions, not only individual researchers, are key to making this work, but are also slower to adapt.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

If you are curious and interested in collaborating, please reach out to anybody on our team, see <https://transparency-certified.github.io/#contact> for contact methods.

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Social Science Data Editors

Description

The “[Social Science Data Editors](#)” group is an ad-hoc collective of (mostly) economics or economics-adjacent active data and reproducibility editors. Most, but not all, of our members work for journals that conduct active computational reproducibility checks.

README template

SSDE also provides a [template README](#) incorporating best practices at social science journals, derived from reviewing over 2,500 replication packages.

The most recent version is available at https://social-science-data-editors.github.io/template_README/.

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7293838](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7293838)

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

The “Social Science Data Editors” group is an ad-hoc collective of (mostly) economics or economics-adjacent active data and reproducibility editors. Most, but not all, of our members work for journals that conduct active computational reproducibility checks. We pragmatically address making standards, policies, tools, and expectations common across many different journals, recognizing that strong standards and policies will depend on the particular discipline, and are driven by and adapted to habits and cultures within disciplines. We differ in our approach to most “data” editors in that we are strongly interested in computational reproducibility, not just data availability, and so tackle the dual problem of making code work, and making data available. Some of our achievements are that many of the top journals in economics, many of which are represented in our working group, now share a common approach to data and code availability, via the Data and Code Availability Standard (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7436134>) we developed, and generally require, or “strongly suggest” a common human-readable descriptive “README” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7293838>) that has greatly improved the quality of the replication packages that journals receive and publish. We

Social Science Data Editors

Fig. 9. Lars Vilhuber, Connolly, Marie, Koren, Miklós, Llull, Joan, and Morrow, Peter. 2022. "A Template README for Social Science Replication Packages". v1.1. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7293838>.

Categories

Policy ▾

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

The working group from the social-science data editors has produced a set of guidelines including a README template for reproducibility packages in the social sciences as well as a data and code availability standard, and a forthcoming author guidance tool. The members' journals sometimes create internal reports on their own replication efforts.

mostly work via a monthly group Zoom (for the active working group) and a more low-volume mailing list. Our members have also consulted with new editors wishing to strengthen their journal's policies, helping in the choice of tools, repositories, policies, and communications, and the growth of the working group over the past 5 years is reflective of that.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

We firmly believe, and our journals have in some form or other stated officially (see [AEA](#), [Econometrica](#), [EJ](#), [JEEA](#)), that data and code used in the analysis of empirical articles must be available, transparent, and openly available, where possible. When data are not easily shareable, due to ethical or unavoidable proprietary rights, authors must be very clear in how others can access such data as well.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

The core challenges we attempt to address through the group are (a) consistency in expectations and application at journals, reflective of evolving community consensus (b) knowledge within the community about modern computational methods that make reproducibility easier - use of old-fashioned methods is detrimental to some aspects of reproducibility, even if it may not be perceived as such within the community (c) broadening access to restricted data for reproducibility checks by at least one set of outside experts - building in access within data use agreements and other access protocols (d) training of the next generation.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Please reach out with any questions, join the mailing list if you want to lurk, or join the monthly call, where we discuss practical questions.

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CODECHECK

Description

CODECHECK is an organization that conducts independent execution of computations underlying research articles. The independent time-stamped runs conducted by codecheckers award a

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

CODECHECK (codecheck.org.uk) is our system for checking whether the computations underlying a

CODECHECK

“certificate of executable computation” and increase availability, discovery and reproducibility of crucial artefacts for computational sciences.

Fig. 10. The CODECHECK example process implementation

Categories

Reproducibility Services ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

This is a community that engages in verification of computer code associated with research papers and studies according to five core principles, with the aim of eliminating errors and removing barriers to reuse of research materials. They provide a certificate to reviewed and verified studies.

research article are reproducible. In particular, we re-run someone else's code with their data to check that we can generate the same (*, for some definition of "same") outputs that appear in the manuscript. We write a certificate summarising our findings and then ensure that all artifacts (code, data, paper) are freely available. It therefore encourages reproducibility and openness by default.

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Certainly by default we would like to say that computational work should be reproducible. I think that in some domains this should be readily achievable, but in many areas this is not yet feasible (see point 3). A simpler vision for now is that I think more journals should reward authors for providing code/data (or reproducible papers). I'd like to see us create an independent organisation which runs something like codecheck as a service for e.g. a large fraction of STEM. Journals or institutions could subscribe to this service to pay for full-time codecheckers.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

a) As compute needs grow, e.g. in machine learning, reproducing work may take significant compute that our codecheck reviewers may not have access to.

b) in clinical domains, openly sharing data is problematic.

There are workarounds for each of (a,b), e.g. providing dummy/synthetic data or small examples.

c) asking reviewers or journals to do more work is further increasing the workload on already overworked researchers.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

a) would anyone like to join us in the search for funding to create the independent organisation that runs codecheck as a service?

b) how do we meaningfully give credit to those that undertake such codecheck reviews if we continue with the same model as peer review (i.e. people do it as a service to their community)?

SciScore

Description

SciScore is a manuscript methods review tool for scientific articles, created at SciCrunch, a California-based company founded on a desire to reduce scientific irreproducibility. Using criteria from various reporting standards (e.g. the NIH, MDAR, STAR methods and ARRIVE), SciScore generates reports and a score for every submission. These automated reviews assist researchers, editors, and funders in improving the quality and reliability of scientific research manuscripts.

Categories

Software & Tools ▾

Evaluation ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

Reproducibility Services ▾

SciScore uses automated methods to assess an article and check which requirements of various established standards have been met. The tool is used primarily by journals, but also by individual researchers, or can be applied at a larger scale to check overall reproducibility compliance for a specific item like unambiguous reference to a code repository or a set of checklist items.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

SciScore highlights to authors who use the tool that new code should be referenced in papers, and tools both commercial and non-commercial should be referenced unambiguously. As it is the only tool that we are aware of that is used at scale by journal publishers we have been able to assess the tool as an intervention with authors who are asked to cite code specifically for their manuscript and those who are asked by the editorial staff and instructions to authors, such as PLoS One. We found that the percentage of authors that routinely reference code repositories (github) in journals in the AACR family (2023 ~16% of papers) is greater as a percentage than those in PLoS One (2023 ~5% of papers).

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

That would be nice, but taking small yet meaningful steps such as unambiguously referring to code would be a really big help towards this goal.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Adoption of the tool by more journals will clearly benefit some measured aspects of reproducibility.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Can you help spread the word that SciScore exists and can help in reproducibility efforts?

FAIRER Data Management

Description

The FAIRER (FAIR + Ethical + Reproducible) GitHub site for development of FAIRER Data Management tools ([FAIRERdata · GitHub](#)), responds to the call for transparent and ethical data stewardship to maintain trust. FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles emphasize machine-actionability and have become a global norm across all data domains. However, data that are FAIR in all respects are not necessarily transparent although ethical and reproducible principles are also required across all domains. The international consortium, [Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa \(CINECA\)](#) has stated that: *"While the FAIR principles have become a guiding technical resource for data sharing, legal and socio-ethical considerations are equally important for a fair data ecosystem . . . FAIR data should be FAIRER, including also ethical and reproducible as key components."*

If our **mission** is to collect and manage world-class scientific data, our **vision** being that scientific data are treated as a publicly available common asset, if our **goal** is state-of-the-art scientific data management, stewardship, and infrastructure that maximizes the value of our scientific data, if our work is grounded in **values** of scientific integrity and excellence and principles of Open Science by-default-by-design, and if our work is agile, enabling, trusted, purposeful, and user-centred, then the **evidence of success** of the mission is **tidy, FAIRER data**.

Contact and feedback: claire.austin@canada.ca

All views and opinions expressed are those of the co-authors, and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of their respective employers, or of any government, agency, or organization.

Categories

Software & Tools -

Evaluation -

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions -

Reproducibility Workflows -

Amongst other tools, FAIRER Data Management includes a [Reproducibility Checklist](#). This interactive questionnaire is suitable for a first level screening estimation of the reproducibility of a particular data asset and associated code. The answers and resulting score can be saved locally. The tool is discipline-agnostic, making it relevant to any scientific field.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

FAIRER Data Management

Reproducible data and code is understood to mean that the final data and code are computationally reproducible within some tolerance interval or defined limits of precision and accuracy, i.e. a 3rd party will be able to verify the data lineage and processing, reanalyze the data and obtain consistent computational results using the same input raw data, computational steps, methods, computer software & code, and conditions of analysis in order to determine if the same result emerges from the reprocessing and reanalysis. "Same result" can mean different things in different contexts: identical measures in a fully deterministic context, the same numeric results but differing in some irrelevant detail, statistically similar results in a non-deterministic context, or validation of a hypothesis.

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Digital Library Federation Assessment Interest Group - Content Reuse Working Group

Description

THE DLF is a primarily (but not exclusively) US-based network of digital library institutions (including universities, museums and archives) that aims to create a robust community of practice to advance research, learning, social justice, and the public good through the creative design and wise application of digital library technologies. It supports a number of working groups that focus on collaborating and "getting things done". It is not exclusively focused on reproducibility but many of the themes explored by the DLF WGs include aspects of reproducibility.

Categories

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions -

The DLF WG on Content Reuse focused on developing the [Digital Content Reuse Assessment Framework Toolkit](#) (D-CRAFT) - a toolkit that helps measure use and reuse of digital objects. It includes a number of assessment methods, tutorials on how to use them, ethical guidelines etc. The group wrote [Towards a Definition of Reuse](#) article. The WG is not exclusively focused on reproducibility, rather interested in reuse broadly, but they consider reproducibility to be an aspect of reuse.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Local Contexts

Description

[Local Contexts](#) is a global initiative that supports Indigenous communities with tools that can reassert cultural authority in heritage collections and data. By focusing on Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property and Indigenous Data Sovereignty, Local Contexts helps Indigenous communities repatriate knowledge and gain control over how data is collected, managed, displayed, accessed, and used in the future.

Contact: Ashley Sosa, ashley.sosa@localcontexts.org, support@localcontexts.org

Categories

Policy ▾

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Reproducibility Workflows ▾

The Local Contexts Labels allow communities to express local and specific conditions for sharing and engaging in future research and relationships in ways that are consistent with already existing community rules, governance, and protocols for using, sharing, and circulating knowledge and data. The Local Contexts Notices are tools for institutions and researchers to identify Indigenous collections and data and recognize Indigenous rights and interests.

These tools, along with the introduction of the Integration Partner certification program and work on [metadata mappings](#) for structures such as Schema.org, allow for better visibility of Indigenous data along with sharing rewards and credit for research outputs from Indigenous data. The FAIR principles alone "creates tension for Indigenous Peoples who are also asserting greater control over the application and use of Indigenous data and Indigenous Knowledge for collective benefit" ([CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, 2019](#)).

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

Whether any scholarship is reproducible, the proper attribution and care should be taken when using Indigenous data. Indigenous interests can change over time, thus, the conditions of access provided by the Indigenous communities for the initial scholarship may not be the same for any following testing.

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Consistency and metadata standards. For those doing the research initially as well as the systems where that data and research is being held/published, there needs to be a consistent effort to include Indigenous communities in the research process. In addition, once included, the metadata for the Indigenous conditions of access and attribution needs to be able to travel with that data. Although Local Contexts has been working on metadata mappings for pre-existing metadata structures, new standards like the [IEEE Recommended Practice for Provenance of Indigenous Peoples' Data](#) help to ensure that Indigenous data sovereignty is in place as a standard practice.

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Do you have a standard practice for Indigenous data?

French Reproducible Research Network

Description

The [French Reproducible Research Network](#) is part of a larger international network bringing together academics who aim to promote and guarantee rigorous research practices by implementing appropriate training activities, designing and evaluating research efforts, improving research, disseminating best practices and working with stakeholders to coordinate efforts across the sector.

Categories

Software & Tools ▾

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Professional Development & Training ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

The French network for reproducible research is a national network of scientists interested in studying the factors that contribute to the robustness of research, promoting training activities and disseminating good practices and recommendations. Reproducibility issues affect all disciplines and the network aims for broad disciplinary representation.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Canadian Research Data Centre Network

Description

The [Canadian Research Data Centre Network](#) (CRDCN) is a network of universities that run secure data facilities for researchers to access sensitive data. The nature of this data and the restricted access makes external verification of reproducibility difficult and therefore internal processes have been developed to enable verification of the output, such as voluntary deposition of a replication package that cross-references the related academic article.

Contact: [Grant Gibson](#) - Assistant Director Research

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

Canadian Research Data Centre Network

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Categories

Software & Tools ▾

CRDCN provides a data service to researchers in Canada working with sensitive data. The group is not directly focused on reproducibility but instead tries to ensure that researchers working with the data provided adhere to reproducible standards/practices as far as possible.

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Knowledge Exchange

Description

[The Knowledge Exchange \(KE\)](#) is an international collaboration of six partner organisations in Europe. In their respective countries, the six partners are responsible for the development of infrastructure and services to support the use of ICT within education and research and in KE they work together to benefit from a trusted platform for the exchange of ambitions and for strategic conversations, optimised return on investment and improved economies of scale, and the combined expertise and/or network from a range of national and international stakeholders. The collaboration currently focuses on Open Access, Open Science, Technology and Infrastructure. KE outputs are influential in developing Open Science across Europe and beyond.

Categories

Reproducibility Workflows ▾

Professional Development & Training ▾

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions ▾

The main output of KE's work is a framework for research institutions to understand how to support and enhance reproducibility practices internally. It can be used as a gap analysis tool and/or to stimulate conversation. It is designed to help users talk about reproducibility at the different organisational levels, identify enablers for scaling up reproducibility and complete an assessment

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

Knowledge Exchange

spreadsheet to help determine your institution's ability to support reproducibility practices, and act as an opener for discussions around maintaining or improving these.

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SciCodes

Description

The [Consortium of Scientific Software Registries and Repositories](#) (SciCodes) represents a diverse group of research software registries and repositories that advocate for open source research software, transparent and reproducible science, standardized and interoperable scientific metadata, and providing credit and recognition to those who create, curate, and maintain the computational methods, tools, and cyberinfrastructure integral to modern scientific research.

Categories

Software & Tools -

Standards, Best Practices, and Definitions -

SciCodes have established best practices for research software registries and repositories and helped research software authors document and publish their computational artifacts with good software engineering and FAIR practices in mind.

Questions & Answers

Briefly, tell us about your work/organization and how it's related to computational reproducibility; What are you trying to address and how?

What is your/your organization's vision when it comes to computational reproducibility (e.g., all scholarship is computationally reproducible by default)?

What are some of the challenges you see to achieving this vision?

What would you like to ask the members of our Interest Group?

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